

Automated argumentation-based social trust negotiation in collaborative networks

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ABSTRACT

Collaboration is an inherent property in Collaborative Networks (CNs), that are increasingly becoming the mainstay of manufacturing and production firms. Collaboration success largely depends on trust. Therefore, trust should be managed in an explicit manner when selecting partners to collaborate with in a CN. Traditionally, the partner selection approaches that explicitly consider trust as a selection criterion manage it as a single concept. However, trust is a multidimensional concept, and each dimension has unique influences on business relationships. The focus of the paper is precisely on the social dimension of trust, which has proven to be of special relevance in CNs. The goal is to allow partners to create alliances where this trust dimension is guaranteed, thus maximizing the chances of successful collaboration. To achieve this, an innovative automated argumentation-based negotiation framework is proposed. In this framework, partners will be modelled as agents in a Multi-Agent System, where automated argumentation techniques are widely used, and they will use different types of arguments to negotiate their social trust requirements. A prototype developed in NetLogo was used to test the proposed framework using the Spanish network on environmental DMAs (Red Española de DMAs Ambientales, REDMAAS), a Spanish thematic research network funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (RED2018-102594-T).

1. Introduction

As defined in [Camarinha-Matos et al. \(2009\)](#), a collaborative network (CN) is a network consisting of a variety of entities (e.g., organizations and people) that are largely autonomous, geographically distributed, and heterogeneous in terms of their operating environment, culture, social capital, and goals. Such entities, to achieve common or compatible goals, make alliances to collaborate and interact using information and communication technologies.

CNs are increasingly becoming the mainstay of manufacturing and production firms ([Camarinha-Matos et al., 2019](#); [Camarinha-Matos, 2014](#); [Durugbo, 2014, 2016](#)) allowing designers, engineers and manufacturers to face the significant challenges arising from the rapidly changing and ever more globalized business environments ([Appio et al., 2017](#)) that have become increasingly volatile, uncertain, complex, and

ambiguous ([vom Brocke et al., 2018](#)). In fact, several recent works have advocated the adoption of CNs as one of the core enablers for Industry 4.0 and the associated digital transformation process ([Camarinha-Matos et al., 2024](#); [Lopez et al., 2023](#)).

By their own definition, collaboration is an inherent property in CNs, and collaboration success largely depends on mutual trust ([Durugbo, 2016](#)). Entering an alliance implies giving up a certain amount of control and creates dependency among the partners ([Vaez-Alaei et al., 2022](#)) so that the success of any partner depends on the actions of the others. Thus, in CNs trust builds on partners' positive expectations about each other's competence and motivations, as well as on a shared acceptance of vulnerability based on the assumption that all partners will act in the best interest of the alliance ([Grossman & Feitosa, 2018](#)). Hence, it is important to create trusting environments that allow partners to believe that their behaviors will lead to favorable results and motivate them to

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collaborate and share knowledge (Davidavičienė et al., 2020). This requires trust to be considered both a precondition and an outcome of collaboration (Morrison et al., 2012) and to be managed as a key variable to all aspects of collaboration throughout the entire life cycle of the CNs (Morrison-Smith & Ruiz, 2020). The life cycle of the CNs comprises the creation, operation, evolution, and dissolution stages (Camarinha-Matos & Afsarmanesh, 1999). This paper deals specifically with the creation stage, where the process of the business alliance formation occurs.

A key activity for business alliance formation is partner selection. In this regard, as shown in Table 1, many partner selection approaches explicitly consider trust as a desirable partner characteristic (i.e., as a partner selection criterion).

However, the previous approaches consider trust as a single concept (a single selection criterion), adopting a monolithic view of it. Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 1, Dunn (2000) stated that trust is composed of an affective element and a cognitive or rational element, which is composed in turn of a technical and a social dimension (Hardwick et al., 2013; Sako, 1992). Particularly, as Mayer and Gavin (2005) indicated, cognitive trust is the key dimension for establishing effective business relationships, since it promotes cooperation and coordination. However, not accounting for its dimensionality could mark important differences since each dimension has unique influences on business relationships (Connelly et al., 2018). For example, people are likely to consider a single integrity failure (social dimension) to be an indicator of a dishonest partner, but they do not consider a single competence failure (technical dimension) to be an indicator of incompetence (Kim et al., 2004). Moreover, people tend to generalize information about integrity across domains of a relationship, but information about a partner's competence is more likely to be domain specific (Connelly et al., 2012).

More specifically, the social dimension of cognitive trust (hereinafter referred to as social trust) takes on special relevance in business relationships since it is an essential component of social capital, understood as the set of features that facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit (Putnam, 1995). In this sense, the literature review shows that the number of social trust related items that are seen as important to the success of a collaboration is vast (cf. e.g., Breuer et al., 2020; de Campos et al., 2019; Costa & Anderson, 2011). The reason is that social factors such as honesty, integrity, professionalism, responsibility, loyalty, etc., are of special interest because partners in a CN must form a society and operate outwardly as a whole; that is, as a single entity by abstracting its internal composition (Mun et al., 2011). If the social aspects of collaboration fail, then the success of the collaboration can be threatened. For example, deficiencies on issues such as honesty or responsibility might compromise the compliance of the agreements on other technical issues like time, cost, or quality. However, in the monolithic view of trust of partner selection approaches in CNs the specific importance of social trust is not addressed since trust is considered a single selection criterion along with many other factors of a

Table 1
Trust in partner selection approaches.

Authors	Selection criteria
Wu and Su (2005) Sarkis et al. (2007)	cost, quality, trust, credit, delivery time, and reliability cultural, business and technical related criteria, with trust being one specific need in the cultural area
Sari et al. (2008) Crispim and Pinho de Sousa (2010)	cost, delivery time, quality, trust, credit, and reliability two main classes of criteria: a) risk, costs, and time factors; and b) other attributes (where trust is located)
Ye (2010) Zhang et al. (2013)	low cost, short time, high trust, low risk, and high quality cost, time, trust, quality, carbon emissions, and lead content
Dong and Wan (2016)	risk, time, cost, reputation (including trust among other indicators like financial status or enterprise image), and quality
Chen and Goh (2019)	compatible culture, willingness to share information, trust and commitment, and advantages complementarily

different nature. This has been an ongoing practice even though the importance and unique influence of this trust dimension on business relationships is known.

The aim of this work is to overcome this problem by addressing the specific importance of social trust when creating a CN. This is done through the definition of an innovative automated argumentation-based negotiation framework that allows partners to specifically negotiate the social trust factors considered relevant to the collaboration and reach an agreement to create an alliance where social trust is guaranteed. It must be a negotiation framework since partners are dealing with subjective and personal aspects of collaboration, so they are the ones that jointly decide what they consider trustworthy according to their convictions or needs and under their responsibility. It must be automated since if the negotiation were done by the partners approaching one another directly through conventional media (e.g., chat and videoconference), this process would be complex and time-consuming because it involves human beings, each with their own personality, requirements, tastes, etc., presenting their negotiation stances and discussing the situation to reach an agreement. However, the rapidly changing and ever more globalized business environments in which CNs operate demand agility and speed. Providing an automated mechanism is in line with the pillar of the recent Industry 5.0 of a human-centric industry, aiming to leverage human agility in collaboration and designing smart/intelligent techniques to collaborate with humans (Maddikunta et al., 2022). It must be an argumentation-based framework since argumentation is the only type of automated negotiation that allows partners to exchange additional information that may influence the counterpart's decision (e.g., a critique or a justification) (Pilotti et al., 2015; Rahwan et al., 2004), which is necessary when negotiating elements as subjective as social trust factors. In the other two major classes of approaches to automated negotiation, namely game-theoretic and heuristic-based approaches, agents can only exchange proposals (i.e., potential agreements), meaning partners are not allowed to exchange social trust related information to try to convince others of their trustworthiness. Finally, it must be innovative since, as discussed below, the current approaches that could be applied to automated social trust negotiation in CNs are not adequate for that purpose since they do not allow partners to handle the subjective nature of social trust factors.

The proposed approach was piloted using the Spanish network on environmental DMAs (Red Española de DMAs Ambientales, REDMAAS), a Spanish thematic research network funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (specifically, REDMAAS2020 was funded from January 2020 to December 2022).

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 analyzes approaches that could be initially applied to automated social trust negotiation in CNs, concluding that none of them properly satisfy its conditions. Section 3 presents the basis for representing the social trust factors of interest and their values that will be used hereafter. Section 4 addresses the necessary three steps to apply argumentation techniques in Multi-Agent Systems (MAS), which is the approach followed in this work since partners are modeled as agents in a MAS. Section 5 details the second of those steps through the definition of the new argumentation-based negotiation framework in the specific context of CNs. Section 6 describes the example of use of the proposed framework in the REDMAAS using a prototype developed in NetLogo. Finally, Section 7 presents the most relevant conclusions and outlines future work.

2. Related work

As previously mentioned, the dimensionality of trust is not considered when selecting partners for creating a CN, meaning that the related work also refers to trust as a single concept (cf. Table 1).

In this regard, when automated trust negotiation is addressed in the literature (cf. e.g., Liu et al., 2013; Squicciarini et al., 2011; Winslett et al., 2009) it is conceived as an authorization mechanism whose aim is the establishment of some level of mutual trust between two parties that

Fig. 1. Dimensionality of trust.

want to exchange online resources and services. It is of special importance in open systems, in which interactions occur among partners that may be unknown to each other (as happens in CNs). In this context, trust negotiation is based on the exchange of credentials and disclosure policies. A credential is a set of identity attributes of an entity used to consider it as trustworthy. The disclosure policies state the conditions (constraints on the attribute credentials) under which a credential can be released during the negotiation. These elements are identified during the negotiation process, within which each party decides which credentials it is willing to disclose to the counterpart and under which conditions.

To apply this mechanism to social trust negotiation when creating a CN, the values of the social trust factors of interest should be defined as credentials for each partner. Additionally, each partner must define the corresponding disclosure policies for determining the conditions under which they are willing to reveal the values of the social trust factors. For example, a partner may not want to reveal that it has a low value on a certain trust factor unless the counterpart meets certain conditions (e.g., the counterpart is also in a similar situation) to avoid being disadvantaged. As can be seen, such a negotiation would be limited to the exchange of social trust values between the partners following certain policies and the success of the negotiation would depend on whether the partners consider the social trust values revealed by the others sufficient to accept them as trustworthy. This may be sufficient when objective data is exchanged (e.g., the partner has an ISO9000 accreditation). However, the subjective nature of social trust makes it insufficient since, as will be discussed in Section 3, partners are not able to provide an exact value for the trust factors but only an approximation of their true value and a confidence interval. Therefore, they must be allowed to exchange additional information that may influence the counterpart's decision (i.e., arguments).

Alternatively, the study of agreement negotiation in CNs reveals that trust is not considered explicitly as a negotiation issue despite being considered as a criterion for partner selection. What is negotiated are other issues such as delivery time, cost, quality or service, among others (cf. e.g., Chen, 2023; Ben Salah et al., 2020; Arrais-Castro et al., 2018; Sadigh et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2010; Wu & Su, 2005). All of them are dynamic issues (i.e., they don't have static values obtained from database), which makes them adequate to be negotiated through an auction process, where automated agents representing the partners exchange proposals and counter-proposals according to a negotiation protocol to reach a mutual agreement.

To apply this mechanism to social trust negotiation when creating a CN, the proposals and counter-proposals must refer to the values of the social trust factors of interest. In this case, a conflict exists when a proponent sends a value on some trust factor lower than the one required by a receiver to agree to collaborate. Note that, in this case, the receiver's required value is a dynamic element, since it is a value decided by the partner as an acceptance threshold. However, the proponent's value is a static element, since it is not decided by the partner, but rather it is the stored value for the trust factor obtained via some

calculation procedure. Therefore, the proponent cannot make a counter-proposal as it cannot change that value. Hence, this type of negotiation cannot be applied to the negotiation of social trust in CNs either. What the proponent must do is try to convince the receiver that although its (subjective) value on the trust factor does not seem to be high enough from the point of view of the receiver, the proponent is indeed trustworthy.

3. Social trust representation

When measuring cognitive trust, trust values on the technical dimension can be usually obtained from raw or statistical project data (e.g., delivery time, costs, and product defects) as well as via other objective methods. However, social trust depends on opinion and must be obtained through questionnaires and/or interviews with partners (cf. e.g., Barki et al., 2015; Fan et al., 2011; and Lavrac et al., 2007).

In this context, let A denote the finite set of partners ($|A| \geq 2$) and F the finite set of social trust factors ($|F| \geq 1$). For measuring social trust in CNs, it is required that after each collaboration between two partners $i, j \in A$, partner i expresses its opinion about the score of partner j in each social trust indicator of interest $f \in F$ (e.g., integrity, participation, proactivity, and responsibility) and regarding the collaboration that has just ended. Partner j does the same for partner i . Therefore, in the first instance, data regarding one partner's trust in another is gathered. Such historical data forms the basis for any higher-level information intended to be obtained. Specifically, what can be of most interest for a partner when it is deciding whether to collaborate with another partner in a CN is to not only know its opinion on, for example, the integrity of the other partner, but also the general opinion on the integrity of that partner. This is intended to ensure the common good since which benefits everyone is good for the alliance and, therefore, for the success of the entire project.

In summary, in CNs there are two main but interrelated perspectives on the trustworthiness of partners when referring to social trust factors (Andrade-Garda et al., 2020): (1) trust of one partner in another partner (peer-to-peer perspective), and (2) the general trustworthiness of a partner (global perspective), usually based on the trust from others.

It is beyond the scope of this paper: (i) to list or impose what are the social trust factors of interest, since they need to be decided for each collaboration; (ii) to list or impose how to use the interview/questionnaire responses to obtain the trust of one partner to another on each decided social trust factor (e.g., partner i 's opinion about partner j 's integrity); and (iii) to specify how to combine this data to obtain higher level indicators (e.g., the general integrity of a partner), since researchers may use or define the method that best suits their situation (e.g., Bayes networks (Haller, 2008), Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Tian & Wang, 2014), and the average of weighted scores (Fan et al., 2011; Lavrac et al., 2007; Msanjila & Afsarmanesh, 2009)). This work starts from the premise that the social trust factors of interest have been decided and that an effective calculation of their values, both at peer-to-peer and global levels, has been done for each partner. Thus, if partners i ,

$j \in A$ have worked together, then the trust of partner i in partner j regarding each relevant trust factor $f \in F$ is known and vice versa. For the purposes of this paper, they are denoted by $T(i, j, f)$ and $T(j, i, f)$ respectively. Moreover, the general trustworthiness of each partner $i \in A$ concerning each trust indicator of interest $f \in F$ is also known. For the purposes of this paper, it is denoted by $T(i, f)$.

Even so, simply having these final values is not enough when it comes to social trust factors. As indicated above, social trust depends on opinion and opinions may be influenced both by internal and external factors at any time. People answering the same social related question in the same conditions at different times need not necessarily give the same result. Thus, the calculated value for a trust factor is not its true value (as opposed to indicators measured via objective methods). It is only an estimation or an approximation to the true value. In this situation, some representation of the human/environmental influence on the values of the social trust factors is needed. In other words, the subjectivity inherent in social trust indicators makes it necessary to explicitly consider it and provide some quantitative indication of it, to allow users to assess the suitability of the results. It is not the aim of this paper to impose how to represent the subjectivity of social trust factors, but it must be calculated in some way and be quantitatively represented. In this regard, for example, the proposal in (Andrade-Garda et al., 2020) represents the subjectivity inherent to social trust factors by its uncertainty of measurement following a metrology-based procedure and includes the standard error of the mean to measure the reliability of the value calculated for each trust factor. Other possibilities in this regard vary from the use of the credibility factor of the feedback source (e.g., (Ruohomaa & Kutvonen, 2010)) to the simple use of the statistical variance (Haller, 2008).

Regardless of how it was calculated, the subjectivity of a trust factor is part of its measurement result, so the value of a trust factor $f \in F$ (both from the peer-to-peer and from the global perspective) will be denoted for the purposes of this work as $R \pm S$, where R is the most likely outcome and S is its subjectivity or reliability. Thus, $T(i, j, f) = R \pm S \forall i, j \in A, f \in F$ (peer-to-peer perspective) and $T(i, f) = R \pm S \forall i \in A, f \in F$ (global perspective), where $[R - S, R + S]$ is the interval within which the true value of the trust factor lies. Likewise, if the values of the trust factor range from a to b (e.g., from 1 to 6 as in (Lavrac et al., 2007)) then the values of S will also do so.

4. Argumentation and MAS

As defined in (van Eemeren et al., 1996), argumentation is a verbal and social activity of reason aimed at increasing (or decreasing) the acceptability of controversial standpoints for the listener or reader, by putting forward a constellation of propositions intended to justify (or refuse) the standpoint before a rational judge. This distinguishes argumentation from the classical deductive reasoning, in which proofs for propositions cannot be contested. Thus, argumentation allows human beings to reach a justifiable conclusion when available information is not complete and/or consistent among participants (Janjua & Hussain, 2012).

The ability to build arguments is crucial for intelligent interactions among human beings in any domain. This makes argumentation theory an interdisciplinary research area (van Eemeren et al., 1996) that has many applications in both theoretical and practical work fields among which Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence stand out (Bech-Capon & Dunne, 2007). In fact, Artificial Intelligence provides an opportunity and methods to transform from human-human negotiation to automated negotiation by implementing agent-oriented modelling (Park et al., 2019). Specifically, Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) is a research area in which argumentation theory has received increasing interest for automated negotiation. The agent-oriented paradigm fits into the use of these types of techniques because agents shape a society in which they interact to make arrangements or to decide future actions. Modelling those interactions using argumentation techniques provides means for

structuring dialogues between participants that have potentially conflicting viewpoints, ensuring that interaction respects certain principles (e.g., consistency of each participant's statements) (Maudet et al., 2007). The combination of MAS and argumentation techniques is applied to fields as different as Group Decision (Carneiro et al., 2019), Project Scheduling (Fu & Zhou, 2021), Cooperative Driving (Mariani et al., 2023), Medical Informatics (Caroprese et al., 2022; Chapman et al., 2019), and Computable Law (Calegari et al., 2020), among many others.

This work applies this combination of MAS and argumentation techniques to negotiate the social trust requirements in the CNs' creation stage since, as indicated in (Rahwan et al. (2004)), automated negotiation is needed when agents have conflicting objectives (in this case, related to social trust requirements) and a desire to cooperate (as happens in CNs). To achieve this, partners (human beings) will be modelled as agents in a MAS, and they will use arguments to negotiate. In this kind of system, and according to (Jennings et al. (1998)), an argument is viewed as a piece of information that may allow an agent to: (a) justify its negotiation stance; or (b) influence another agent's negotiation stance. Thus, in addition to accepting or rejecting a proposal, an agent can offer more information. The information that can be exchanged can be a justification of a proposal, stating why an agent makes such a proposal or why the counterpart should accept it; or a critique, making it possible to change the other agent's region of acceptability.

In this paper argumentation techniques and MAS are applied for a real-life application and, following (Carrera and Iglesias (2015)), to achieve this it is necessary to address three different steps in each specific context: (i) analyze the suitability of these techniques, (ii) select an argumentation framework, and (iii) choose a MAS platform. These steps are discussed below for the specific context of social trust negotiation in the creation of CNs.

4.1. Suitability analysis

This first step refers to evaluating the suitability of argumentation techniques for the considered problem. Since argumentation techniques define mechanisms for carrying out complex and sophisticated dialogues, they are suitable for designing agents that interact among themselves, offering and processing reasons; that is, rational agents. This perfectly fits the needs of the CNs' creation stage, where partners (rational human beings) engage in dialogue to defend their social trustworthiness and try to convince the doubtful ones that it is a good decision to collaborate with them. Thus, partners are seen as agents that negotiate the social trust aspects of collaboration by using arguments to: (a) justify their social trustworthiness; or (b) influence another partner's opinion about their social trustworthiness.

4.2. Select an argumentation framework

The classical argumentation proposal of (Dung (1995)) defines a basic argumentation framework as a pair $\langle AR, attacks \rangle$, where AR is the set of arguments, and $attacks$ denotes a binary relation on AR . For two arguments A and B , $attacks(A, B)$ indicates that A represents an attack against B . Consequently, whether or not a rational agent believes in a statement depends on whether or not the argument supporting this statement can be successfully defended against the counterarguments (i. e., the attacks). Moreover, Dung's proposal presents the notion of acceptability based on that attack relation between two arguments and proposes a set of semantics for reasoning.

A characteristic of Dung's argumentative framework is that it considers only one type of argument for explanation or justification-oriented purposes in presence of inconsistency. However, later works on argumentation-based negotiation have argued that arguments may be of different natures (Amgoud & Prade, 2005). Particularly, *rewards*, *threats*, and different types of *appeals* are helpful for negotiation. These types of arguments have been successfully used in many argumentation-

based frameworks such as the ones proposed in [Monteserin and Amandi \(2011\)](#), [Rahwan et al. \(2004\)](#), and [Kraus et al. \(1998\)](#).

Specifically, *appeals* are used to justify a proposal; *rewards* are used to promise a future reward; and *threats* are used to warn about negative consequences in case the counterpart does not accept a proposal. In addition, four types of *appeals* are presented in [Kraus et al. \(1998\)](#): (1) *appeal* to past promise, to remind the counterpart a promise made in the past if it refuses to execute the action; (2) *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples, to convey to the counterpart a contradiction between what it says and past actions; (3) *appeal* to “prevailing practice”, to convey to the counterpart that accepting the proposal of action will further its goals since it has furthered other’s goals in the past; and (4) *appeal* to self-interest, to convince a counterpart that taking this action is also good for said counterpart. As proved in [Amgoud and Prade \(2005\)](#), Dung’s framework only considers *appeals* to “prevailing practice”, to past promise, and to counterexamples.

The inclusion of more types of arguments makes argumentation frameworks richer, as it allows negotiating agents to satisfy both individual and shared goals. This is in line with the philosophy of CNs, where the aim is to ensure the common good since which is good for everyone is good for the alliance, and therefore, for the success of the entire project. Therefore, the negotiation framework presented in this work will consider the above-mentioned four types of *appeals*, *rewards*, and *threats* as acceptable arguments.

With respect to the structure of the negotiation framework, [Rahwan et al. \(2004\)](#) state that, abstractly, it can be viewed in terms of its negotiation agents and the external elements representing the environment in which these agents interact. These elements external to the agent are the domain language, the communication language, the negotiation protocol, and the information stores. Of course, they must be adapted for the specific domain under consideration. These elements are briefly introduced in the following and fully adapted to social trust negotiation in CNs in [Section 5](#):

- **Domain language (DL):** The DL allows agents to refer to the concepts of the environment. In argumentation frameworks, agents need richer DLs to be able to exchange argumentative information. For example, in the framework presented in [Sierra et al. \(1997\)](#), the DL defines variables representing negotiation attributes, constants representing values for the negotiation attributes, and includes equality and conjunction.
- **Communication language (CL):** The CL is the language that facilitates communication between agents. Thus, when a statement in DL is exchanged between agents, it is given a particular meaning by the CL locution that encapsulates it. In MAS, the Knowledge Query and Manipulation Language (KQML) ([Mayfield et al., 1996](#)) and the Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agent’s Agent Communication Language (FIPA ACL, 2002) are the two major CL proposals. However, as indicated in [Rahwan et al. \(2004\)](#) they fail to capture all the locutions needed in an argument-based negotiation framework, which often makes designers choose to provide their own negotiation specific locutions with the appropriate semantics of the message within them.
- **Information stores:** To carry out the argumentation process and take advantage of the automated negotiation it is necessary to have appropriate information stores to keep accessible information during interaction. These stores allow maintaining the agents’ relevant information as well as the history of negotiation commitments for future references. Moreover, as indicated in [Rahwan et al. \(2004\)](#), they make it possible to control some protocol-related behaviors. For example, preventing an agent from denying a promise it has previously made.
- **Negotiation protocol:** A negotiation protocol defines a set of conventions governing the interaction among participants, thus constraining the use of the language. Designing the rules of a protocol

amounts to specifying what counts as a legal conversation between agents involved in an interaction ([Maudet et al., 2007](#)).

4.3. Choose a MAS platform

Finally, the above-mentioned third step proposed by [Carrera and Iglesias \(2015\)](#) refers to selecting the MAS platform that supports the argumentation framework. As the authors themselves indicate, there is not a widely accepted argumentative platform for MAS, thus researchers should extend the selected MAS framework to support the argumentation facilities needed. In this work, a [NetLogo \(2023\)](#) implementation of the proposed approach has been developed to illustrate its operation in a reader-friendly manner (cf. [Section 6](#)), so that researchers can easily extend their selected MAS framework to deploy our proposal.

5. Proposed argumentation-based negotiation framework

As indicated in [Section 4.2](#), the structural elements of a negotiation framework must be adapted for the specific domain under consideration. Thus, this section presents the DL, the CL, the information stores, and the negotiation protocol specifically designed for social trust negotiation in the creation of CNs, which together constitute the proposed argumentation-based negotiation framework.

5.1. Domain language and communication language

Regarding the DL and inspired by the work of [Sierra et al. \(1997\)](#), variables are used to represent the social trust factors that are subject to collective negotiation and their attributes; constants are used to represent the values of R and S for those trust factors (as defined in [Section 3](#)) and the related attributes; and, also, it includes comparison operators and conjunction. Thus, an example of a resulting construction is: $(T(i, j, Integrity) = 3 \pm 0.5) \wedge (T(j, Integrity) = 2.0 \pm 1.0)$.

Regarding the CL, and in addition to the basic locutions included in the traditional automated negotiation mechanisms (i.e., *open* and *close* dialogue; *propose*, for making proposals; *accept*, for accepting proposals; and *reject*, for rejecting proposals ([Karunatillake et al., 2009](#))), locutions to represent the argument types that the agents can generate are needed ([Rahwan et al., 2004](#)). In this case, as previously indicated, we adopt the three general argument types that are considered in the literature about argumentation-based negotiation: *appeals*, *rewards*, and *threats*. With regard to *appeals*, we consider the four types presented in ([Kraus et al., 1998](#)). The structure and meaning of these locutions are detailed in [Section 5.3](#).

5.2. Information stores

When defining a negotiation framework, it is necessary to consider how to store the relevant information to be generated or accessed during the negotiation. In this work, conceptually, each agent has two independent but related repositories. The first one is called the *trust store* (TS) and the second is called the *commitment store* (CS). These information stores make it possible to exploit the full potential of automatic negotiation, since it would not be possible to handle all this information efficiently in a traditional face-to-face negotiation.

The TS maintains the agent’s values of trust for each trust factor as set out in [Section 3](#). Thus, it is composed of two data structures representing the partner’s trustworthiness at peer-to-peer and global levels. The CS maintains the commitments incurred by the partners in negotiations.

Regarding the data modeling which makes it possible to create the TS and CS of each agent, [Fig. 2](#) and [Fig. 3](#) show respectively the excerpts of the Entity-Relationship diagram (ERD) for representing the global and peer-to-peer perspectives of the social trustworthiness of partners. As may be seen, there is a binary relation “has global value” between the Agent and Social Trust Factor entity types with cardinality of many-to-

Fig. 2. ERD for agents' trustworthiness at global level.

Fig. 3. ERD for agents' trustworthiness at peer-to-peer level.

many (N:M) and a partial (optional) participation. This means that: i) an agent can have global values for many social trust factors but not all agents need to have global values for the social trust factors (e.g., an agent representing a new partner that has never participated in an alliance); and ii) a social trust factor can have global values for many partners but there could be social trust factors without global values for any partner (e.g., a newly defined social trust factor). The relationship defines the attributes R and S representing $T(i, f) = R \pm S, \forall i \in A, f \in F$. Analogously, there is a ternary relationship between the Agent and Social Trust Factor entity types with cardinality of many-to-many (N:M:P) and a partial (optional) participation. It is a ternary relationship because the entity type Agent appears twice representing that peer-to-peer values are referred to trust of one partner to another. The relationship defines the attributes R and S representing $T(i, j, f) = R \pm S, \forall i, j \in A, f \in F$. For its part, Fig. 4 shows the extract of the ERD for representing the commitments incurred in negotiations. As can be seen, there is a ternary relationship “has committed to” between the Agent (twice for representing the proponent and the respondent agent) and Social Trust Factor entity types with cardinality of many-to-many (N:M:P) and a partial (optional) participation. This relationship defines the attributes R and S , representing the committed social trust factor value and its subjectivity; *level* indicating if the social trust factor was negotiated at peer-to-peer or global level; *case* representing the involved argumentation case in the negotiation (cf. Section 5.4), and *st* as a binary value provided by the receiver after collaboration indicating if the decision to accept the

proposal/appeal/reward was correct (i.e., if the receiver would do it again because the collaboration results were satisfactory).

In the ERD transformation to a relational model, a cross-reference table is created to map each many-to-many relationship. Thus, as shown in Tables 2–4, three tables “has global value”, “has peer-to-peer value”, and “has committed to” are created in which each row stores a dedicated identifier (defined for simplicity), and the primary keys of tables Agent (twice in the case of “has peer-to-peer value” and “has committed to”) and Trust Factor, along with the defined attributes for each relationship.

Hence, for each agent $i \in A$ there will be n rows in the table “has global value”, where n is the number of social trust factors that i had negotiated, and which will conform the global level data structure of its TS. Each of these rows contains the general opinion about i on each trust factor $f \in F$ (i.e., $T(i, f) = R \pm S$). Analogously, for each agent $i \in A$ there will be m rows in the table “has peer-to-peer value”, where m is the number of partners with whom partner i has collaborated, and which

Table 2

Example of rows in the table “has global value”.

<i>id</i>	<i>ag</i>	<i>tf</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>
0	<i>i</i>	Integrity	2.0	0.5
1	<i>j</i>	Integrity	4.0	0.0
2	<i>k</i>	Integrity	2.8	1.0

Fig. 4. ERD for the commitments incurred in negotiations.

Table 3

Example of rows in the table “has peer-to-peer value”.

<i>id</i>	<i>ag1</i>	<i>ag2</i>	<i>tf</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>
0	<i>j</i>	<i>i</i>	Integrity	2.9	0.3
1	<i>k</i>	<i>i</i>	Integrity	4.1	0.1
2	<i>i</i>	<i>j</i>	Integrity	2.7	1.0
3	<i>i</i>	<i>k</i>	Integrity	3.5	0.2

Table 4

Example of rows in the table “has committed to”.

<i>id</i>	<i>ag_p</i>	<i>ag_r</i>	<i>tf</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>level</i>	<i>case</i>	<i>st</i>
0	<i>j</i>	<i>i</i>	Integrity	2.0	0.5	1	3	1
1	<i>j</i>	<i>i</i>	Integrity	0.0	6.0	2	24	0
2	<i>i</i>	<i>j</i>	Integrity	2.0	1.0	2	24	1
3	<i>j</i>	<i>i</i>	null	null	null	null	25	null
4	<i>j</i>	<i>i</i>	Integrity	4.0	0.2	1	25	null

will form the peer-to-peer level data structure of its TS. Each of these rows contains i 's opinion about j ($j \in A, j \neq i$) on each social trust factor of interest $f \in F$ (i.e., $T(i, j, f) = R \pm S$). Finally, for each agent $i \in A$ there will be r rows in the table “has committed to”, which will form its CS, where r is the number of negotiations in which i participated as respondent, and: (i) an agreement was reached by an accepted proposal, *appeal*, or *reward*, or (ii) the negotiation ended because a *threat* was rejected (thus the proponent has the commitment to fulfil the *threat*). Only with information on past commitments it is possible to make *appeals* such as an *appeal* to “prevailing practice”, an *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples, and an *appeal* to past promises; or to reject proposals because of past threats in future negotiations. Regarding the attributes of this last table, it should be mentioned that *level* = 1 means peer-to-peer level and *level* = 2 means global level; *null* values in *tf*, *R*, *S*, and *level*, mean respectively “any trust factor”, “no likely value”, “no subjectivity”, and “any level”; and the field *st* only makes sense when an agreement has been reached and the partners have collaborated so it takes the value *null* otherwise. Thus, for example, the first record in Table 4 means that in a past negotiation agent i accepted $T(i, j, Integrity) = 2.0 \pm 0.5$ from agent j after a Case 3 *appeal* and that the collaboration results were satisfactory. The second record means that in a past negotiation agent i accepted the *reward* from agent j of accepting any global value of *integrity* in a future negotiation and that the collaboration results were unsatisfactory (it would not do it again). The fact that the collaboration results, from agent i 's point of view, were not satisfactory does not exempt j from the obligation of keeping its promise. Once j fulfils its promise, the record can be removed from the CS. In the third record, agent j accepted the *reward* from agent i for accepting $T(i, j, Integrity) = 2.0 \pm 1.0$ in a future negotiation and the collaboration results were satisfactory. The fourth record means that agent i rejected the *threat* from agent j of rejecting any of agent i 's proposal in a future negotiation whatever the trust factor and level under negotiation, and the values of *R* and *S* sent by agent i . Finally, the fifth record means that agent i rejected agent j 's *threat* of rejecting any of agent i 's future proposals unless the proposed trust value of the trust factor *Integrity* at peer-to-peer level is equal to or greater than 4.0 ± 0.2 and no other value will be accepted.

All data in the agents' TS and CS are accessible to all agents participating in the dialogue, but only each agent can update its own information (the other agents can only read it). Thus, in the same vein as in Panisson et al. (2015), agents can build an acceptable argument in a social trust negotiation both from their TS and CS and from those of the other participants.

5.3. Negotiation protocol

Before starting the negotiation, partners must manually introduce

their negotiation attributes (i.e., their social trust factors of interest at peer-to-peer and/or global level) and the required values for each one (*R* and *S*) in their local interfaces. In addition, each partner must select a rejecting mode, that indicates the system when to reject an *appeal* during negotiation. For the purposes of this work, four rejecting modes are defined, namely *Never*, *Always*, *On Demand*, and *Scored*. In *Never* mode, if an *appeal* is acceptable for the receiver it is accepted, and no rejection argument is sought. In *Always* mode, the system always tries to find an argument to reject any *appeal*. In *On demand* mode, the system always asks the partner behind the agent if it wants to accept the *appeal* or find an argument for rejection. Finally, in *Scored* mode, the partner specifies an acceptance lower bound on an *appeal* strength scale. This acceptance bound only applies to *appeals* to self-interest, which are the only ones for which strength is defined. Thus, on an *appeal* to self-interest, the system checks whether its strength reaches the specified acceptance level. If so, it is accepted, otherwise it is rejected. Section 5.4.4 addresses how to calculate the strength of an *appeal* to self-interest. For the other types of *appeals* (i.e., *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples, *appeal* to “prevailing practice”, and *appeal* to past promise), the partner must select between *Never*, *Always*, and *On Demand* mode.

Once the negotiation attributes and the rejecting mode are configured in the local interface of each partner, the negotiation is carried out between automated agents according to a negotiation protocol. The negotiation protocol defined in this work is synthesized in Fig. 5. The nodes in the graph represent the various communication predicates allowed in the protocol (legal locutions further described below) while the edges denote the legal transitions permitted between these distinct dialogue moves. It is inspired by the work in Karunatillake et al. (2009), considering in this case five main stages (sections with dotted lines in Fig. 5): (i) opening, (ii) conflict recognition, (iii) conflict management, (iv) agreement, and (v) closing; that are described in the following:

- Opening and closing: These stages provide the important synchronization point for agents involved in the dialogue, the former indicating its beginning and the latter its ending.
- Conflict recognition: The initial interaction between the agents brings the conflict to the surface.
- Conflict management: This stage allows agents to negotiate, thus addressing the conflict. The resulting negotiation dialogue in this stage is composed of an exchange of arguments.
- Agreement: An encounter ends if all agents utter an acceptance locution or if at least one agent utters a rejection locution, and the receiver has nothing to argue against it. The negotiation ends, either with the participants agreeing to collaborate or agreeing to abort the initiative and abandon the business opportunity.

The stage “Conflict diagnosis” proposed in Karunatillake et al. (2009) is deliberately omitted here, since the only conflict addressed in this work is that the social trust requirements are not satisfied for the creation of the CN, and it is assumed that partners will attempt to manage and resolve it through a collaborative dialogue.

The stages of the proposed protocol are subject to the following constraining rules:

- The first stage in every negotiation is Opening.
- The last stage in every negotiation is Closing.
- The Opening stage may occur only once in any negotiation since no new partners are admitted once the negotiation has started.
- The Conflict recognition stage must precede every other stage, except Opening.
- The Agreement stage can be entered both following the Conflict recognition and the Conflict management stages, depending on whether the initial proposal is accepted or not.
- The Closing stage can only be entered following the Agreement stage since no agent can leave the negotiation before it has concluded having accepted or refused to collaborate.

Fig. 5. Proposed negotiation protocol.

In addition to these constraints, since the Conflict management stage is composed of an exchange of arguments, the argument selection mechanism to determine the sequence of the arguments exchanged when a proposal is rejected must be decided. As indicated in Pilotti et al. (2015), an argument selection mechanism should provide an answer to the following question: Given a set of proposals that an agent may send to its counterpart, which is the most appropriate from the point of view of the speaker?

In the case of social trust negotiation in CNs, the following is true: (i) trust is the issue to negotiate; (ii) there is no exchange of goods or money, and (iii) there is a single objective common to all the participants, which is to collaborate with social trust guarantees. In this context, an argument selection mechanism in line with the one proposed in the work of Kraus et al. (1998) is considered the most appropriate. Thus, arguments are selected according to their severity. The underlying idea is that a partner would progress from less aggressive arguments up to the most aggressive ones. It should not be forgotten that the aim is to carry out a friendly negotiation, where the partners can justify their social trustworthiness without any of them feeling attacked or intimidated. This way, the argument selection order in the CNs' context is set as follows: (1) *appeal* to self-interest, (2) *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples, (3) *appeal* to “prevailing practice”, (4) *appeal* to past promises, (5) promise of a future *reward*, and (6) *threat*. In this case, *appeal* to self-interest ranks first because it is the most common reason for appeal in real-life negotiations in CNs and no partner feels attacked. Also, *appeal* to precedents ranks second because counterexamples make the receiving agent change its mind more quickly and easily than an *appeal* to “prevailing practice” (Amgoul & Prade, 2005). The remaining arguments are ranked as in the work of Kraus et al. (1998). Section 5.4 details the different argumentation cases that can occur when a proposal is rejected following this argument selection mechanism.

Once the protocol constraints and the argument sequence are defined, a specification of the legal locutions for the negotiation dialogue between two agents $i, j \in A$ regarding a trust factor $f \in F$ at peer-to-peer or global level can be provided. The descriptive structure defined

for the locutions is an adaptation of the one provided by McBurney et al. (2003). In this case, the descriptor “Information Store Updated” has been omitted as the TS is not modified during a social trust negotiation. Instead, the descriptors “Data from the TS” and “Data from the CS” have been added, in order to clarify the origin of the data included in locutions. The locutions are numbered sequentially from L1 to L8.

L1: The *open-dialogue(.)* locution

Locution: *open-dialogue*(i, j), where $i, j \in A$.

Preconditions: This locution must not already have been uttered.

Meaning: The speaker, agent i , opens a dialogue with the receiver, agent j . A dialogue can only commence with this move.

Response: No response required. The dialogue is automatically established.

Data from the TS: None.

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: No effects.

L2: The *propose(.)* locution

Locution: *propose*(i, j, α), where $i, j \in A$; α in the form of $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(i, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$.

Preconditions: Agent i must have previously uttered a locution *open-dialogue*(i, j).

Meaning: The proponent, agent i , proposes to the receiver, agent j , to accept to collaborate with a social trustworthiness of α .

Response: If the receiver finds α acceptable, it utters a locution *accept*(j, i, α), otherwise it utters a locution *reject*(j, i, α, β).

Data from the TS: α .

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: No effects.

L3: The *accept(.)* locution

Locution: $\text{accept}(i, j, \alpha)$, where $i, j \in A$; α in the form of $T(i, j, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(j, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$.

Preconditions: Agent j must have previously uttered a locution $\text{propose}(j, i, \alpha)$, $\text{appeal}(j, i, \alpha, \delta)$, $\text{reward}(j, i, \alpha, \mu)$, or $\text{threaten}(j, i, \alpha, \gamma)$.

Meaning: Agent i accepts to collaborate with agent j with a social trustworthiness of α .

Response: No response required.

Data from the TS: α .

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: A record is created with the data of the agreement (accepted α). If a reward is also accepted, a new record is created to register it.

L4: The **reject(.)** locution

Locution: $\text{reject}(i, j, \alpha, \beta)$, where $i, j \in A$; α in the form of $T(i, j, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(j, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$; β containing:

1. $T(i, j, f) = b \pm s_2$ or $T(j, f) = b \pm s_2$ the trust value required by agent i to collaborate.
2. $\text{threaten}(i, j, \text{null}, \text{reject}(i, j, \alpha'))$ for rejecting a proposal because of a past threat.
3. $\text{accept}(i, k, \alpha') \wedge st = 0$, where $k \in A$, for rejecting an *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples.
4. $\text{accept}(k, j, \alpha') \wedge st = 0$, where $k \in A, k \neq i$, for rejecting an *appeal* to “prevailing practice”.
5. *null* for rejecting a reward or a threat, since no reason is needed to reject them.
6. “Appeal not strong enough” for rejecting an *appeal* to self-interest in *Scored* rejection mode.

A locution $\text{accept}(\cdot)$ as part of β represents a past accepted proposal or *appeal*.

Preconditions: Agent j must have previously uttered a locution $\text{propose}(j, i, \alpha)$, $\text{appeal}(j, i, \alpha, \delta)$, $\text{reward}(j, i, \alpha, \mu)$, or $\text{threaten}(j, i, \alpha, \gamma)$

Meaning: Agent i rejects to collaborate with agent j with a social trustworthiness of α for the reason β .

Response: The response depends on what is being rejected. The response is generated following the presented argument selection mechanism.

Data from the TS: α .

Data from the CS: β in cases 2, 3, and 4.

CS Updates: If a threat is rejected a new record is created with the data of the future harm.

L5: The **appeal(.)** locution

Locution: $\text{appeal}(i, j, \alpha, \delta)$, where $i, j \in A$; α in the form of $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(i, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$; and δ the argument to accept α . All types of appeals adhere to this structure. However, the type of appeal that is being sent depends on what is argued in δ . Thus, if δ contains:

1. $\text{accept}(j, k, \alpha') \wedge st = 1$, where $k \in A$, it is an *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples.
2. $\text{accept}(k, i, \alpha') \wedge st = 1$, where $k \in A, k \neq j$, it is an *appeal* to “prevailing practice”.
3. $\text{reward}(j, i, \text{null}, \text{accept}(j, i, \alpha'))$, it is an *appeal* to past promise. Otherwise, it is an *appeal* to self-interest.

Locutions $\text{accept}(\cdot)$ and $\text{reward}(\cdot)$ as part of δ represent a past accepted proposal, *appeal*, or *reward*.

Preconditions: Agent j must have previously uttered a locution $\text{reject}(j, i, \alpha, \beta)$ to a locution $\text{propose}(i, j, \alpha)$ or for other $\text{appeal}(i, j, \alpha, \delta')$ being δ' a previous argument to accept α .

Meaning: Agent i appeals to agent j to accept to collaborate with a social trustworthiness of α in face of the argument δ .

Response: If the receiver finds δ persuasive it utters a locution $\text{accept}(j, i, \alpha)$, otherwise it utters a locution $\text{reject}(j, i, \alpha, \beta)$, being β the new argument for rejecting α .

Data from the TS: α .

Data from the CS: δ when other than an *appeal* to self-interest is sent.

CS Updates: No effects.

L6: The **reward(.)** locution

Locution: $\text{reward}(i, j, \alpha, \mu)$, where $i, j \in A$; α in the form of $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(i, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$; and μ the future reward in the form of $\text{accept}(i, j, \alpha')$.

Preconditions: Agent i must have previously uttered a locution $\text{appeal}(i, j, \alpha, \delta)$ that has been rejected by agent j , and agent i has nothing else to appeal.

Meaning: Agent i promises to agent j the future reward μ if it accepts to collaborate with a social trustworthiness of α .

Response: If the receiver finds μ persuasive it utters a locution $\text{accept}(j, i, \alpha)$, otherwise it utters a locution $\text{reject}(j, i, \alpha, \text{null})$.

Data from the TS: α .

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: No effects.

L7: The **threaten(.)** locution

Locution: $\text{threaten}(i, j, \alpha, \gamma)$, where $i, j \in A$; α in the form $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$ or $T(i, f) = a \pm s_1, f \in F$; and γ the future harm in the form $\text{reject}(i, j, \alpha', \text{null})$.

Preconditions: Agent i must have previously uttered a locution $\text{reward}(i, j, \alpha, \mu)$ that must have been rejected by agent j .

Meaning: Agent i threatens agent j with the future harm γ if it does not accept a social trustworthiness of α to collaborate.

Response: If the receiver finds γ persuasive it utters a locution $\text{accept}(j, i, \alpha)$, otherwise it utters a locution $\text{reject}(j, i, \alpha, \text{null})$.

Data from the TS: None.

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: None

L8: The **close-dialogue(.)** locution

Locution: $\text{close-dialogue}(i, j)$, where $i, j \in A$.

Preconditions: Agent j must have previously uttered a locution $\text{accept}(j, i, \alpha)$ or a locution $\text{reject}(j, i, \alpha, \beta)$ in response of a locution $\text{threaten}(i, j, \alpha, \gamma)$.

Meaning: Agent i announces to agent j the end of the dialogue.

Response: No response required.

Data from the TS: None.

Data from the CS: None.

CS Updates: No effects.

5.4. Argumentation cases

The first negotiation step in the Conflict recognition stage of the proposed negotiation protocol is for each agent to propose collaborating to the others indicating its trustworthiness with respect to the trust factors of interest. Each partner receives the proposals and decides for each one if it is an acceptable proposal or not. A proposal is directly accepted when the value of R sent by the proponent is equal to or greater than the value of R required by the receiver, and the value of S sent by the proponent is less than or equal to the value of S required by the receiver. For example, when the proponent ($j \in A$) sends $T(i, j, \text{Integrity}) = 3.5 \pm 0.6$ and the receiver ($i \in A$) requires $T(i, j, \text{Integrity}) = 3.0 \pm 0.8$. Otherwise, the proposal is initially rejected. This applies for all the trust factors of interest both at peer-to-peer and global level.

As previously indicated, when a proposal is rejected, the proponent must appeal to try to convince the receiver of its trustworthiness so that the receiver accepts the proposal even if it does not reach the required values of R and/or S . If appealing is not possible, then the proponent will proceed with the promise of a reward and, if it is not accepted either, with the formulation of a threat.

In the following, the different argumentation cases that can occur when a proposal is rejected are considered. They are numbered from 1 to 25 and cases 1, 6, 10, 11, 14, and 21 to 25 are illustrated in Fig. 6 since they are the most representative ones. Peer-to-peer values are used to illustrate the argumentation cases, where $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$ denotes the value of agent i (the proponent) on the trust factor f from the point of view of agent j (the receiver) and $T_r(j, i, f) = b \pm s_2$ denotes the corresponding value required by agent j (the subscript r in T_r is used to differentiate between the proposed and the required values). Global values can equally be used as illustrated in Fig. 7.

Argumentation cases 1 to 20 refer to *appeal* to self-interest cases, and the necessary information for making these *appeals* is stored in the agents' TS. Cases 21 to 25 refer to argumentation cases where other than *appeal* to self-interest are needed as well as those cases when *rewards* or *threats* are presented. In these cases, it will be necessary to use information both from the agents' TS and CS. In all cases, if an agreement is reached, it must be stored in the CS as shown in Table 4.

5.4.1. Appeal to self-interest

Appeal to self-interest arguments are divided into three blocks: (i) *appeal* arguments when $\neg R \wedge S$; that is, when the value of R sent by agent i is less than the value of R required by agent j ($a < b$); (ii) *appeal*

arguments when $R \wedge \neg S$; that is, when the value of S sent by agent i is greater than the value of S required by agent j ($s_1 > s_2$); and (iii) *appeal* arguments when $\neg R \wedge \neg S$; that is, when the value of R sent by agent i is less than the value of R required by agent j and the value of S sent by agent i is greater than the value of S required by agent j ($a < b$ and $s_1 > s_2$).

The necessary information for making these *appeals* is stored in the agents' TS and involves the argumentation items (AI) presented in Table 5.

In AI 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 it is necessary to specify what *close to* means. For the purposes of this work, one value is *close to* another when the difference is no greater than a quarter of s_2 (the maximum subjectivity accepted by the receiver). Thus, for example, if a value of 3.0 ± 0.8 is required for the trust factor Integrity, then a value in the interval $[2.8, 3.0]$ is close to the lowest acceptable value 3.0.

An argument can be composed of one or more AI, and they are the basis to calculate the strength of the argument to be used in the *Scored* rejection mode (cf. Section 5.4.4). Table 6 shows the 20 possible *appeal* to self-interest argumentation cases, along with the AIs of which they are comprised.

In Cases 1 and 10, all the possible values of agent i on the trust indicator are acceptable for agent j (i.e., fall within the acceptance interval of values of agent j or are greater than those values). That is, AI1 and AI0 are respectively fulfilled. In this case, there is no reason for agent j to continue rejecting the proposal and it is accepted.

In addition, note that if AI3 is true then AI5 and AI7 are also true. Analogously, if AI5 or AI7 is true then AI9 is true. Also, AI7 is implicit in Cases 11, 12, 13, and 14, otherwise $\neg S$ would not be fulfilled. These are

Fig. 6. Argumentation cases.

Fig. 7. Case 1 with global level values for trust factor f .

Table 5
Argumentation items (AI).

AI	Expression	Description
0	$a-s_1 \geq b$	Agent i 's lowest possible value of the social trust factor is equal to or greater than the value of R required by agent j .
1	$a-s_1 \geq b-s_2$	Agent i 's lowest possible value of the social trust factor is equal to or greater than the lowest value accepted by agent j .
2	$a-s_1$ close to $b-s_2$	Agent i 's lowest possible value of the social trust factor is close to the lowest value accepted by agent j .
3	$a \geq b$	The value of R sent by agent i is greater than or equal to the value of R required by agent j .
4	a close to b	The value of R sent by agent i is close to the value of R required by agent j .
5	$a \geq b-s_2$	The value of R sent by agent i is equal to greater than the lowest value accepted by agent j .
6	a close to $b-s_2$	The value of R sent by agent i is close to the lowest value accepted by agent j .
7	$a + s_1 \geq b$	Agent i 's best value for the social trust factor is equal or greater than the value required by agent j .
8	$a + s_1$ close to b	Agent i 's best value for the social trust factor is close to the value required by agent j .
9	$a + s_1 \geq b-s_2$	Agent i 's best value for the trust factor is equal to or greater than the lowest value accepted by agent j .
10	$a + s_1$ close to $b-s_2$	Agent i 's best value for the trust factor is close to the lowest value accepted by agent j .

Table 6
Appeal to self-interest argumentation cases.

	Case	AIs
$\neg R \wedge S$	1	1
	2	5 (9)
	3	5 7 (9)
	4	5 8 (9)
	5	5 2 (9)
	6	5 2 7 (9)
	7	8
	8	9
	9	10
$R \wedge \neg S$	10	0
	11	3 2 (7)
	12	3 (7)
$\neg R \wedge \neg S$	13	4 (7) (9)
	14	4 2 (7) (9)
	15	7 (9)
	16	7 5 (9)
	17	8
	18	8 6
	19	9
	20	10

the reasons for the AIs that appear in parentheses in Table 6.

5.4.2. Other appeal cases

When an *appeal* to self-interest is not possible or is rejected, another type of *appeal* must be sent (cf. Section 3.2). In this situation, the following three cases arise:

- Case 21. *Appeal to precedents as counterexamples*. For a social trust factor (both at peer-to-peer and at global level), agent i says to agent j that in the past it accepted (from agent i or from another agent) an equal or lower trust value than the one that is now being rejected, and that the collaboration result was satisfactory. To build this argument, it is necessary to check agent j 's CS looking for a record representing a past acceptance in these conditions. If several records meet the conditions, the most recent one will be chosen. Fig. 6 shows an example of this case and also illustrates that agent j rejects the *appeal* to precedents providing another counterexample, which is that in the past it accepted from agent $l \in A$ an equal or lower trust value than the one that is now being rejected, and that the collaboration result was unsatisfactory. This argument is constructed analogously from agent j 's CS.
- Case 22. *Appeal to "prevailing practice"*. For a social trust factor (both at peer-to-peer and at global level), agent i says to agent j that in the past agent $k \in A$ accepted an equal or lower trust value from it, and that the collaboration result was satisfactory. To build this argument it is necessary to check agent k 's CS looking for a record representing a past acceptance in these conditions. If several records meet the conditions, the most recent one will be chosen. Fig. 6 shows an example of this case and also illustrates that agent j rejects the *appeal* to "prevailing practice" arguing that it knows that in the past agent $l \in A$ accepted from agent i an equal or lower trust value than the one that is now being rejected, and that the collaboration result was unsatisfactory (i.e., it does not want to take the risk). This information is obtained analogously from agent l 's CS. Of course, agent j could also send the same rejection argument as in case 21.
- Case 23. *Appeal to past promises*. For a social trust factor (both at peer-to-peer and at global level), agent i says to agent j that it must accept the proposed trust value because in the past it promised it as a reward. This information is obtained from agent i 's CS (cf. e.g., record with id 1 in Table 4). An *appeal* to a past promise cannot be rejected.

In cases 21 and 22, for the situation to be analogous, if the *appeal* is made as a response to the rejection of another *appeal*, the record selected from the CS to build the argument must represent an acceptance on the same *appeal* case as the current one that is being rejected. This is done by checking the value of the field *case*. In case 23, the value of the field *case* must be 24 (representing a stored accepted *reward*). In addition, the value of *st* must be 1 in cases 21 and 22 and it is indifferent in case 23 (a promise must be kept whether the collaboration was successful or not).

5.4.3. Rewards and threats

When an *appeal* is not possible or when they have all been rejected, it's time for agent *i* to promise a future *reward* if agent *j* accepts the proposal. If this *reward* is not accepted, all that remains for agent *i* to do is to send a *threat* (cf. Section 5.3). Since what is being negotiated is social trust in the CN's creation stage, the *rewards* and *threats* must refer to this. Other negotiation issues are out of the scope of this framework. Thus, the last two argumentation cases are as follows:

- Case 24. *Reward*. For a social trust factor (both at peer-to-peer and at global level), agent *i* promises a future reward to agent *j* if it accepts the proposed trust value. Thus, agent *i* could promise to agent *j* that in a future negotiation it will accept a low value or even any value for the trust factor. If agent *j* accepts the *reward*, the information is stored in its CS for future usage (cf. e.g., record with *id* 2 in Table 4).
- Case 25. *Threat*. For a social trust factor (both at peer-to-peer and at global level), agent *i* threatens agent *j* with future harm if it does not accept the proposed trust value. Thus, agent *i* could threaten agent *j* to reject any value of the trust factor in a future negotiation between them, or that it will not accept a value lower than a given one (and no appeal will be accepted) (cf. e.g., records with *id* 3 and 4 in Table 4). For example, the argument *reject*(*i*, *j*, $T(i, j, f) < c \pm s_3$, *null*) in Fig. 6 represents the future harm of rejecting a value of $T(i, j, f)$ lower than $c \pm s_3$ for no other reason than to fulfil the *threat* (β is *null* in the location). An example of rejecting a proposal because a past *threat* is also shown in Fig. 6 after Case 25, where β is the past *threat* constructed from a record in agent *i*'s CS where $ag.p = j$, $if = f$, $level = 1$, $R = c$, $S = s_3$, $case = 25$, and $st = null$ (if the *threat* was rejected, the collaboration did not happen). The future harm γ in β is *null*, since in this case agent *j* is not threatening agent *i* but telling agent *i* that it is rejecting the proposal because it is fulfilling a past *threat*.

5.4.4. Strength calculation

As stated in Section 5.3, an important issue in the negotiation protocol is when to reject an *appeal*. Specifically, four rejecting modes are defined: *Never*, *Always*, *On Demand*, and *Scored*. In *Scored* mode, the partner specifies an acceptance lower bound based on the strength of the received *appeal* to self-interest. Only argumentation cases with a strong enough *appeal* will be accepted. Therefore, a mechanism to calculate the strength of each *appeal* to self-interest argumentation case is required.

To achieve the above, for each *appeal* to self-interest argumentation case it is necessary to analyze the strength of the involved AIs. Thus, since AI0 and AI1 imply the direct acceptance of the argument (Case 1 and Case 10), they are left out of the calculation process and A2 to AI10 will be evaluated on a scale of 1 to 9.

Let $i, j \in A$, $T(j, i, f) = a \pm s_1$, and $T_r(j, i, f) = b \pm s_2$ be the data involved in a proposal from agent *i* to agent *j* rejected by agent *j*. If this does not fit Case 1 or Case 10, what is most important is that all possible values of $T(j, i, f)$ are acceptable or close to being acceptable values for agent *j*. This occurs when AI2 is fulfilled. Therefore, AI2 receives the score 9.

One might think that AI3 has more value than AI2 since $a \geq b$. However, remember that *a* is only an estimation of the value of $T(j, i, f)$ and the true value falls in the interval $[a-s_1, a+s_1]$. Note that with high values of s_1 the range of possible values of $T(j, i, f)$ is expanded and many of them may be far from $b-s_2$ (lowest value of $T(j, i, f)$ that agent *j* would accept). For this reason, AI3 receives the score 8 instead of 9, and AI4 receives the score 7 since it does not guarantee that $a \geq b$ but that *a* should be close to *b*.

If a case does not fulfil the previous AIs, the most desirable thing is that the value of *a* is an acceptable or close to being acceptable value for agent *j*. This happens, respectively, with AI5 and AI6, so AI5 receives the score 6 and AI6 receives the score 5.

All that remains to be evaluated are the AIs that involve reasoning with $a + s_1$. Following the same reasoning, AI7 and AI8 receive, respectively, the scores 4 and 3 since they guarantee, respectively, that $a + s_1 \geq b$ and $a + s_1$ is close to *b*. The scores 2 and 1 are for AI9 and AI10 respectively, since they only guarantee that $a + s_1$ is an acceptable or close to being acceptable value for agent *j*.

Applying the scores to the *appeal* to self-interest argumentation cases, the ranking in Table 7 is obtained.

6. Illustrative example

6.1. The REDMAAS

The REDMAAS network is formed by 8 groups involved in the measurement of atmospheric particle size distributions by means of Differential Mobility Analyzers (DMAs). These groups are University Institute of Environment of the University of A Coruña (IUMA-UDC), Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research of the Spanish National Research Council (IDÆA-CSIC), National Institute of Aerospace Technology (INTA), Izaña Atmospheric Research Centre of the State Meteorological Agency of Spain (IARC-AEMET), University of Granada, Mediterranean Center for Environmental Studies (CEAM), University of León, and Center for Energy, Environmental and Technological Research (CIEMAT). The network has been working since 2010 (Gómez-Moreno et al., 2015) and has as its main objective the cooperation between the groups to solve common problems and to optimize their facilities and protocols. The main activities developed in the network include: i) DMA calibration, ii) CPC and SMPS intercomparison, iii) measurement quality control program and iv) support for the radioactive facility license. In sum, it is a CN designed to consolidate the activities among the Spanish groups involved in the observation of the atmospheric particle size distributions and of the particle number concentration, that are essential attributes to the study of the effects of the particulate matter on health. This data allows researchers to estimate, for example, the fraction of the particles that settle in the lungs and different parts of the respiratory system and even those that can penetrate the bloodstream.

6.2. Social trust in the REDMAAS

As part of the REDMAAS operation, the research groups join efforts to perform particle sampling campaigns in different places around Spain, involving several activities such as instrument calibration, sampling of different elements with specialized instruments, analysis of samples in laboratory, statistical analysis, interpretation of results, reporting, etc. (cf., e.g., Sorribas et al., 2022; Gómez-Moreno et al., 2023).

During a sampling campaign, research groups must behave as a perfectly orchestrated working unit so as not to put the quality of the data and its future treatment at risk. This is achieved by considering both technical and social trust issues when creating the campaign team. Thus, every time a sampling campaign must be conducted, the research groups

Table 7
Ranking of *appeal* to self-interest argumentation cases.

Case	AIs	Total score
11	3 2 (7) (5) (9)	29
14	4 2 (7) (9)	22
6	5 2 7 (9)	21
12	3 (7) (5) (9)	20
5	5 2 (9)	17
13	4 (7) (9)	13
3, 16	5 7 (9)	12
4	5 8 (9)	11
18	8 6	8
2	5 (9)	8
15	7 (9)	6
7, 17	8	3
8, 19	9	2
9, 20	10	1

in the REDMAAS must negotiate to determine which of them will participate in it and with what responsibilities. Firstly, technical issues are discussed (e.g., if a specific measurement instrument is required only the groups having this instrument can participate). After that, other social issues (e.g., past experiences or affinities) are negotiated between the groups satisfying the technical requirements. In this regard, before applying the proposed method the situation was as follows:

- Negotiations were mainly done by conventional means (e-mail, audio/video conference, etc.).
- Social trust issues arose informally in the conversations and were informally discussed.
- There was no common understanding of the social trust issues discussed in the conversations.
- Past experiences were the basis for the negotiation. However, no past collaboration data was formally registered, so the negotiation was based on what the groups' members in the conversation remembered about past collaborations or on what others had told them about it.
- Decisions were made more based on preconceived ideas or intuition than on reliable data. This led groups to make certain assumptions about mutual behavior that were sometimes not met.

In order to apply the proposed method and improve this situation, a series of meetings facilitated by the REDMAAS2020 coordinator were held with the heads of the research groups. These meetings were focused on the determination of the social trust aspects of collaboration that were of interest to them. That is, those which were informally, implicitly, or even unconsciously addressed in conversations during the previous negotiations: Open communication, Assertiveness, Proactivity, Availability, and Versatility, among others. Consequently, the research groups in the REDMAAS now consider the social trust factors of interest for collaboration in an explicit way, and an agreement exists on their meaning to ensure a common understanding.

6.3. Negotiation example

A prototype of the proposed framework was implemented in Net-Logo, since it is a friendly multi-agent programmable modeling environment known by most participating groups. Thus, each of the 8 research groups in the REDMAAS was represented as an anonymized agent in the prototype.

In the following, an example of execution of the above-mentioned prototype is presented, considering four agents (a0 to a3) representing four research groups negotiating the social trust factor *Proactivity* at the peer-to-peer level. In this context, the starting point is the following:

- **Table 8** shows the peer-to-peer values obtained from the agents' TS. Thus, for example, $T(a0, a1, Proactivity) = 2.5 \pm 0.5$ and $T(a1, a0, Proactivity) = 3.0 \pm 0.4$.
- **Table 9** shows the peer-to-peer values that each agent initially requires from the others to agree to collaborate. Thus, for example, $T_r(a0, a1, Proactivity) = 3.0 \pm 0.5$ and $T_r(a1, a0, Proactivity) = 2.5 \pm 0.5$.
- **Tables 10–12** show extracts of the CS of a0, a2, and a3 with the data of interest for the *appeals* to precedents as counterexamples, to “prevailing practice”, and to past promises involved in this example.

Table 8
Peer-to-peer values of Proactivity.

	a0		a1		a2		a3	
	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S
a0	–	–	2.5	0.5	2.0	0.8	3.0	1.8
a1	3.0	0.4	–	–	2.1	0.6	3.2	0.9
a2	2.0	0.9	2.0	0.6	–	–	2.3	0.8
a3	2.9	0.6	2.8	0.9	3.0	0.5	–	–

Table 9
Required peer-to-peer values of Proactivity.

	a0		a1		a2		a3	
	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	S
a0	–	–	3.0	0.5	3.0	0.6	2.0	0.2
a1	2.5	0.5	–	–	3.0	0.8	2.5	0.8
a2	2.5	0.1	3.0	1.0	–	–	2.8	1.1
a3	2.9	0.5	3.0	0.8	2.8	0.3	–	–

Table 10
Extract of the CS of a0.

id	ag.p	tf	R	S	level	case	st
0	a3	Proactivity	2.0	0.5	1	3	1
1	a2	Proactivity	2.4	0.5	1	3	0
2	a1	Proactivity	2.7	1.1	1	13	1
3	a2	Proactivity	0.0	6.0	1	24	null

Table 11
Extract of the CS of a3.

id	ag.p	tf	R	S	level	case	st
0	a1	Proactivity	2.5	1.0	1	19	1

Table 12
Extract of the CS of a2.

id	ag.p	tf	R	S	level	case	st
0	a1	Proactivity	2.8	1.0	1	13	0

They are also used to building arguments for rejecting *appeals* in some cases.

The corresponding output of the negotiation dialogue between the four agents considered in this example is presented in **Fig. 8**. In the prototype, for each agent *a* involved in the negotiation dialogue and trust factor *f*, *a.R* is the most likely value of *f* (i.e., *R*), *a.BV* is the best possible value of *f* (i.e., *R + S*), *a.LV* is the worst possible value of *f* (i.e., *R – S*), *a.LB* is the lowest value of *f* accepted by *a*, and *a.UB* is the upper bound of the acceptance interval of *a* for the trust factor *f*.

For the purposes of this paper, a “breed” representing the agents has been defined: *breed [agents A]*. It is internally specified as *agents-own [id name tsp tsg cm tp_r tg_r prs bound]*, where *id* is the identifier of the agent required to uniquely identify it; *name* is the denomination of the agent; *tsp* is the list of peer-to-peer values of the agent; *tsg* is the list of global level values of the agent (not used in this example); *cs* is the list of commitments of the agent; *tp_r* is the list of the peer-to-peer values required by the agent from the other agents and for the interest trust factors (in this case, *Proactivity*); *tg_r* is the list of the global level values required by the agent from the other agents and for the interest trust factors (not used in this example); *pr*s is the list of the proposals received by the agent; and *bound* is the acceptance lower bound for the strength of the received *appeal* to self-interest (it is assumed that the partners had selected the rejection mode *ScoreD*). These *bound* values are randomly generated for illustrative purposes. Analogously, the values of *R* and *S* sent in *rewards* and *threats* are also randomly generated and accepted/rejected. In the prototype, the lists *tsp* and *tsg* represent the TS of the agent and the list *cs* represents its CS. For the purposes of this prototype, they are built from data obtained from the tables presented in **Section 5.2**. The lists *tp_r* and *tg_r* are directly built from data in text files. Locations are shown using near-natural language so that the partners (human beings) can understand what is happening in the negotiation.

The negotiation dialogue presented in **Fig. 8** is as follows:

Fig. 8. NetLogo output for the considered example.

- The proposals from a0 to a1 (line 1) and from a2 to a3 (line 9) are directly accepted since they meet the requirements for the trust factor Proactivity at the peer-to-peer level (lines 13 and 14).
- The proposal from a0 to a2 (line 2) is initially rejected for not meeting the requirements (line 20), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a0 (line 35) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 36).

No *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples or to prevailing practice can be sent, so a0 reminds a2 of the past promise of accepting any value of Proactivity at peer-to-peer level (line 53). Therefore, a2 is under the obligation to accept (line 54).

- The proposal from a0 to a3 (line 3) is initially rejected (line 23), but the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a0 (line 41) is strong enough to be

accepted by a3 (line 42). The same applies to the proposals from a3 to a0 (lines 10, 17, 29, and 30), from a3 to a1 (lines 11, 19, 33, and 34), and from a3 to a2 (lines 12, 22, 39, and 40).

- The proposal from a2 to a0 (line 7) is initially rejected (line 16), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a2 (line 27) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 28). An *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples is sent by a2 arguing that a0 accepted a value of 2.0 ± 0.9 from a1 in the past and the collaboration was satisfactory (line 47). This argument is accepted by a0 (line 48).
- The proposal from a1 to a0 (line 4) is initially rejected (line 15), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a1 (line 25) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 26). An *appeal* to precedents as counterexamples is sent by a1 arguing that a0 accepted a value of 2.0 ± 0.5 from a3 in the past and the collaboration was satisfactory (line 45). This *appeal* is rejected by a0 arguing that it also accepted a value of 2.4 ± 0.5 from a2 in the past and the collaboration was not satisfactory (line 46). An *appeal* to prevailing practice is sent by a1 in response arguing that a2 accepted a value of 2.5 ± 1.0 from it in the past and the collaboration was satisfactory for a2 (line 49). This argument is accepted by a0 (line 50).
- The proposal from a2 to a1 (line 8) is initially rejected (line 18), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a2 (line 31) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 32). Since a2 has nothing to appeal, it promises a2 the *reward* of accepting a value of Proactivity at peer-to-peer level equal to or greater than 1.5 ± 0.7 in a future negotiation (line 55). The *reward* is accepted by a1 (line 56).
- The proposal from a1 to a2 (line 5) is initially rejected (line 21), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a1 (line 37) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 38). Since a1 has nothing to appeal, it promises a2 the *reward* of accepting a value of Proactivity at peer-to-peer level equal to or greater than 2.2 ± 0.8 in a future negotiation (line 57). The *reward* is not accepted by a2 (line 58) and, in consequence, all that remains is for a1 to threaten a2. In this case, the *threat* consisted in not accepting a value of Proactivity at peer-to-peer level equal to or less than 3.3 ± 0.1 in a future negotiation (line 61). In view of this *threat*, a2 decided to accept to collaborate with a1 (line 62).
- The proposal from a1 to a3 (line 6) is initially rejected (line 24), and the *appeal* to self-interest sent by a1 (line 43) is not strong enough to be accepted (line 44). *Appeal* to precedents as counterexamples is not possible, but *appeal* to prevailing practice is. Thus, a1 argues that in the past a0 accepted a value of 2.7 ± 1.1 from it and the collaboration was satisfactory (line 51). This *appeal* is rejected by a3 arguing that in the past it accepted a value of 2.8 ± 1.0 from a1 and the collaboration was not satisfactory (line 52). In response, a1 promises a3 the *reward* of accepting a value of Proactivity at peer-to-peer level equal to or greater than 2.0 ± 1.8 in a future negotiation (line 59). The promise is accepted by a3 (line 60).

All agents agreed to collaborate at the end of the negotiation, so the campaign team can be created.

6.4. Discussion

6.4.1. Computational complexity

The computational complexity of the code developed for the prototype in NetLogo is $O(n^2 * m)$, where $n = |A|$ (in this case $n = 8$ since REDMAAS is formed by 8 research groups) and m is the length of *tsp* which is, as previously mentioned, the list of peer-to-peer values in the agent's TS. This complexity is caused by the three nested while loop shown in Fig. 9.

To give these values meaning, it is necessary to remember that, as indicated in Section 3, after each collaboration between two partners $i, j \in A$, partner i expresses its opinion about the score of partner j in each social trust factor of interest $f \in F$, and partner j does the same for partner i . Thus, after each collaboration $t * p * (p - 1)$ data are generated, where t is the number of opined social trust factors and p the number of involved

```

to propose
  while [i < nagents]
  [
    while [j < nagents]
    [
      if (i != j)[
        set aux ([tsp] of A i)
        while [k < length aux and not found]
        [

```

Fig. 9. Extract of NetLogo code for the prototype.

partners ($t \leq |F|, p \leq |A|$). This data is used to update the values of the social trust factors in the agents' *tsp* or to create them if there were social trust factors not considered in previous negotiations (so no records exist for them). The corresponding global level values of those social trust factors are also correspondingly updated or created in the agents' *tsg*.

In the CNs creation stage, negotiating a large number of social trust factors is not expected to be the case, so that the *tsg* of each agent is expected to be a small repository (e.g. if partner i has negotiated 20 trust factors throughout their full collaboration history, then the *tsg* of agent i will have 20 records representing the global opinion about its trust-worthiness on each of those factors). For its part, the size of the *tsp* of each agent i (i.e., m) depends both on the number of different partners with whom partner i has collaborated and on the number of social trust factors negotiated, so it is expected to be greater than the *tsg* but also of small size (e.g., if partner i has collaborated with 30 partners and 20 trust factors have been negotiated, then the *tsg* of agent i will have a maximum of 600 records). Obviously, for a large number of partners the amount of data in the agents' TS proportionally increases.

6.4.2. Outcomes

In order to compare the outcome obtained through the prototype with that obtained through conventional means, the organizer of each campaign was asked to register which groups tried to negotiate to form the campaign team and the result of each negotiation. In this respect, it should be noted that the prototype did not always obtain the same result as the conventional negotiation. There were negotiations marked by the organizer as failed and marked by the prototype as successful. The groups indicated that they failed to reach an agreement to form the campaign team at that moment, but they recognized that it would have been a good team for the campaign and that the proposed approach would have helped them to reach an agreement. Likewise, there were negotiations marked by the organizer as successful (i.e., the negotiating groups formed the campaign team) and marked by the prototype as failed. After analyzing these cases, the prototype response was perceived as reasonable by the involved research groups, given the specific social trust factors negotiated, and the acceptance intervals established by the groups for them. This is because, as indicated previously, conventional negotiation is more informal and less rigorous in these social aspects, which makes it possible to reach agreements that would not be reached otherwise. For this reason, it is important for the groups to be very careful when establishing the values of R and S required for each social trust factor of interest to prevent blocking effective alliances.

6.4.3. Users' satisfaction

In the initial prototype conception phase, the research groups considered that it could be tedious to have to negotiate each social trust factor individually. However, when the social trust factors of interest for the REDMAAS were identified by the groups they understood the peculiarities of each one and the need to manage them separately. In fact, the trust factors to negotiate do not have to be the same for all the groups in a negotiation. For example, proactivity may be an important trust

factor for group i and for group j it may not be. In this case, there would be a negotiation dialogue about proactivity between the agent representing group i and the rest of the agents but not between the agent representing group j and the rest of the agents. This was highly appreciated by the groups in the REDMAAS as it allows them to focus the negotiation on their needs without being conditioned by the requirements of the rest, which is highly difficult in negotiation through conventional means. Finally, the negotiations are based on available data about past collaborations and negotiations stored in the TS and CS of each agent and not on memories or opinions, which makes the results more reliable.

7. Conclusion and future work

Trust is a critical issue for partners interested in creating a CN, since the success of future collaboration largely depends on it. This is evidenced by the fact that many partner selection approaches consider trust as a partner selection criterion. However, they manage it as a single concept, and it is known that trust is a multidimensional concept with each dimension having unique influences on business relationships. Particularly, this paper addresses the social dimension of trust and how partners entering a CN can be assured that the other partners with whom they will collaborate are reliable in that regard.

The way to achieve the above in the rapidly changing and ever more globalized business environments in which CNs operate is through providing partners with an automated way to negotiate the social trust requirements for collaboration before starting the collaboration and reaching an agreement on them. However, the current approaches that could be applied to automated social trust negotiation in CNs are not adequate for that purpose since they do not allow partners to handle the subjective nature of social trust factors. Because of this, an innovative automated negotiation approach was proposed. The type of automated negotiation adopted is argumentation, since it is the only one that allows partners to exchange additional information with the aim of defending their trustworthiness and convincing the others to accept collaborating with them. The designed argumentation framework includes the argument types reported in literature; namely the four types of *appeals*, *rewards*, and *threats*, thus allowing rich negotiation dialogues between agents. In addition, domain-specific DL, CL, information stores, and the negotiation protocol are defined. To put the framework into operation, partners are modelled as agents in a MAS, and they can configure the MAS before each negotiation to specify how they want the agents representing them to behave when faced with certain types of arguments. In the end, the responsibility of deciding whether to collaborate or not always lies with the partners (human beings). Thus, if all partners agree to collaborate, the CN is created and the first stage of the life cycle of the CN ends. Otherwise, the CN cannot be created, and the business opportunity will be lost.

This has been represented in a prototype implemented in NetLogo and piloted using the REDMAAS to present an example of use and demonstrate its applicability. Thanks to the good reviews received from the participants, it is under consideration to incorporate its functionality in a web application called ESCAPE, which is the evolution of SCALA (Andrade-Garda et al., 2019) and that is used by the REDMAAS research groups for managing the sample campaigns. Also, the REDMAAS participants especially appreciated the usefulness of the strength calculation for *appeals* to self-interest and its application in the *Scored* rejection mode. Accordingly, the authors are working on the application of the concept of strength to the remaining arguments (cf. e.g., Morveli Espinoza et al. (2020) for the strength calculation of threats) in the context of CNs.

In order to optimize the negotiation process, a technique that could complement the proposal in this paper is graph model theory (Zhang et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2025), in which decision makers (in this case, partners), their options, their preferences, and the feasible states can be analyzed in order to guide the negotiation process to achieve a desired

solution. With this method, if the desired outcome (i.e., the agreement) cannot be achieved under the given state concept (i.e., the conditions are not in place for the agreement), the partners' preferences that lead to the desired solution must be determined. This way, it would be possible to identify the best courses of action to negotiate to obtain an agreement, thus strengthening the negotiation process. Continuing with this line of improvement, the minimum-cost consensus-based failure mode and effect analysis (MMC-FMEA) framework (Zhang et al., 2023) could be used to detect and prioritize the risks that could threaten the success of the negotiation (e.g., the foreseeable behavior of a partner) and they could be given more attention.

Another future research issue is how to deal with dishonest behavior by partners when negotiating social trust. It is true that dishonest behavior is not the expected behavior, since in CNs the aim is not so much on the individual but on the collective success. Partners come together to address business opportunities that they could not undertake individually, so that the success of the alliance is the success of everybody. However, it does not mean that this behavior cannot occur. For example, partner i could strategically establish its $T_i(i, j, f)$ to benefit or disadvantage the acceptance of certain partner j . To detect this type of situation it would be necessary to analyze the information stores presented in Section 5.2 to identify anomalous behavior from partners. This can be done through the application of machine learning techniques (e.g., artificial neural networks, support vector machines or the K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm) for example, in the first step of the Proposing stage of the proposed negotiation protocol.

Finally, another future research issue is that, once the CN is created, social trust must continue to be managed throughout the entire life cycle of the CN; that is, in the remaining stages of operation, evolution, and dissolution. The authors are working precisely on that and, more specifically, on the operation and evolution stages. In this regard, since the evolution of the CN happens during its operation, these two stages are usually integrated into a single stage called "dynamic operation" (Huang et al., 2002). A critical situation that may occur during "dynamic operation" is the need for reconfiguration. Partners may need to change their roles, scheduling or financial problems may arise, a partner can leave the alliance, etc. In these circumstances, it is crucial for the success of the collaboration to properly identify and manage the issues related to the social trustworthiness between the partners that may arise in order to maintain the climate of trust and not harm the collaboration. For this purpose, the authors are currently designing a mechanism that involves the automated reconfiguration of the CN by exploring the information stored (i.e., the partners' TS and CS) and the renegotiation of the responsibilities of each partner in the alliance. This automated mechanism will provide agility and speed to the process and, like the proposal presented in this paper for social trust negotiation in the creation of the CN, will prevent the problems that may arise when partners must reach a reconfiguration agreement in which social trust is guaranteed by directly approaching one another.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Javier Andrade-Garda: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Víctor Carneiro-Díaz:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Daniel Lage-Etchart:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sonia Suárez-Garaboa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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